

Training Manual 1

Sustainable Agriculture and Aquaponic practices

Minimizing environmental impacts

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Introduction

The environment can be defined as a total of all living and non-living things within the surroundings in which human beings, plants and animals live. The state of the environment can affect and influence human life, and human activities can also alter the environment around them. In the same way, Aquaculture and aquaponics practices can have an impact on the environment. It is therefore important to understand what those impacts could be and how to minimize them.

Module Objectives

At the end of this module, men and women participants will,

- Gain an understanding of the environment and how it affects human well being
- Understand the impacts of aquaculture and aquaponics practices on the environment.
- Understand the relevant strategies for mitigating environmental impacts of aquaculture and aquaponics practices

Module Timing, Location, and Materials required

No	Session	Estimated time	Location
1.	Definition of the environment and its benefits to human well being	2 hrs	Lead Farmer's Home
2.	Introduction to Aquaculture	2 hrs	
3.	Environmental Challenges in Aquaculture	2 hrs	
4.	How Aquaponics may offer solutions to environmental challenges	2 hrs	

Training Materials: Power point presentation/illustrations, Flip charts, pens and pencils

Session 1: Definition of the environment and its benefits to human well being

Interactive Activity 1: Group Activity

Divide the participants in four groups (two for men and two for women). Each group with examples, should discuss their understanding of the environment, with. They should also list some of the benefits they get from their environment. In a plenary session, each group should share a summary of their ideas followed by a general group discussion of the main themes identified and any differences among the groups.

Facilitator's Notes

What is the environment?

An Environment is everything that is around us, which includes both living and nonliving things such as soil, water, animals and plants.

How does the environment affect human wellbeing?

The environment provides several ecosystem goods like water, land for growing crops, habitats for wildlife. The environment also provides services like water purification, flood mitigation, nutrient cycling, and climate regulation.

How do human activities alter the environment?

Human activities alter the environment in many ways as indicated in figure 1. For example, agricultural activities may lead to removal of natural vegetation cover, which may affect evapotranspiration, and surface runoff. In addition, agricultural and industrial activities lead to release of waste products into the environment, which can impact the quality of water (which humans depend on), and air that we breath and this could lead to many diseases impacting humans and animals.

Figure 1: Impacts of human activities and their feedback mechanisms

Session 2: Introduction to Aquaculture

Interactive Activity 2: Group Exercise

Divide the participants in four groups (two for men and two for women). Each group should discuss their understanding of aquaculture, and the benefits from aquaculture. In a plenary session, each group should share a summary of their ideas followed by a general group discussion of the main themes identified and any differences among the groups.

Facilitator's Notes

What is aquaculture?

Aquaculture is the production of aquatic organisms under controlled conditions throughout part or all their lifecycle. Aquaculture production takes place in all types of water environments including ponds, rivers, lakes, the ocean, and man-made systems on land.

What are the benefits of aquaculture?

Aquaculture reduces the burden on natural resources, and contributes to attaining food security for different communities. In addition, aquaculture can be used to rebuild populations of threatened or endangered aquatic species. Figure 2 shows the different components of aquaculture farming that contribute to the sustainability of the environment.

Figure 2: Illustration of Aquaculture farming

Source: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sustainable_fish_farming_009.jpg
(License: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.en>)

Session 3: Environmental Challenges in Aquaculture

Interactive Activity 3: Peer to Peer

- Take a walk with the person next to you and have a conversation on some of the environmental challenges in aquaculture systems
- On individual flash cards, write down the two most important environmental challenges that have you observed and hand these over to the facilitator
- In a plenary session, the facilitator reads out some of the flashes and clusters them in them on the wall

Facilitator's Notes

What are the environmental challenges in aquaculture?

In many areas, aquaculture has led to the destruction of natural ecosystems. Figure 3 shows the different environmental challenges in aquaculture.

Figure 3: Environmental impacts of Aquaculture

- **Destruction of ecosystems:** Aquaculture can lead to the clearing of natural habitats such as mangroves, wetlands, and coastal forests to build ponds and cages. This reduces biodiversity, disrupts food chains, and removes natural barriers that protect coastlines from erosion and storms.
- **Soil salinization:** In coastal aquaculture, saltwater ponds can cause salt to seep into surrounding soils and groundwater. This makes the land unsuitable for agriculture, reduces soil fertility, and can damage nearby freshwater ecosystems and crops.
- **Water pollution:** Fish waste, uneaten feed, and chemicals from aquaculture ponds can enter rivers, lakes, and coastal waters. This increases nutrient levels, causing algal blooms and oxygen depletion (eutrophication), which can kill fish and other aquatic organisms.
- **Contaminants in water and soil:** Antibiotics, pesticides, disinfectants, and other chemicals used to control diseases and parasites can accumulate in water and sediments. These contaminants can harm aquatic life, enter the food chain, and pose risks to human health.

What strategies can minimize environmental pollution from aquaculture?

- Select sites for aquaculture that may not impact other activities especially agricultural activities
- Select indigenous instead of exotic species
- Understand the biology and ecology of species to be farmed
- The type of farming infrastructure (i.e pond versus floating) and size should be selected based on the type of species, as well as land and water availability
- Plan for treatment of effluent from the farm before releasing it into the environment (inlet and out design)
- Improve feed and avoid excessive use to reduce feed waste
- Investment in Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS)
- Investment in Aquaponics

Session 4: How Aquaponics offer solutions to environmental challenges

Interactive Activity 4: Brainstorming

- Ask the participants to list strategies ways in which aquaponics may offer solutions to environmental challenges of aquaculture
- On a flip chart, write down the different strategies that have been mentioned by the participants and group them into similar themes

Facilitator's Notes

What is Aquaponics?

Aquaponics is a production system that combines the growing of aquatic animals and plants. In such a system, the plants are usually grown in an environment without soil, a practice called hydroponics. Therefore the word “Aquaponics” is a combination of the words “Aquaculture” and “hydroponics” as indicated in figure 4.

bottom left: fish tanks and water collection tanks;

Figure 4: Aquaculture and Aquaponic systems

How can aquaponics help to mitigate impacts of aquaculture?

- Reduced habitat destruction because they are in controlled environment
- Reduced pollution of water bodies
- Reduced negative effects on ecology because there is a lesser chance of escape of exotic species to mix with indigenous species

Why aquaponics is not widely adopted in developing countries

- High initial cost of designing the system
- High cost of operation and maintenance
- Lack of skills/expertise of farmers in running the system
- When infection occurs, the whole system needs to be emptied and disinfected
- Requires a short response time in case of technical/human failures

Module Key Messages

- Aquaculture is the production of aquatic organisms under controlled conditions throughout part or all their lifecycle
- Aquaculture reduces the burden on natural resources, and contributes to attaining food security for different communities
- However, aquaculture has a number of negative impacts on the environment, which include destruction of the natural environment, and pollution of water and soil.
- One strategy to mitigate environmental impacts of aquaculture is to invest in Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) or aquaponics.
- However, aquaponics requires a high investment for the design as well for operating and maintenance costs

Reflection Exercise for Participants

Now that you have an idea about aquaculture, its impacts on the environment and strategies that can be used to mitigate environmental impacts. Write out the key message on flash card and hangs it up on the wall. As a plenary, a gallery walk is instituted so that all participant read the messages of other participants.

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